
PROFILING CRIMINALS IN NIGERIA: EXAMINING THE DIFFICULTIES AND PROSPECTS FOR ENHANCING INVESTIGATIVE CAPABILITIES WITHIN THE NIGERIA POLICE FORCE

Ogbaje Jenekwu USMAN

Department of Sociology, Faculty of Social Sciences,
Prince Abubakar Audu University,
Anyigba, Kogi State –Nigeria
Tel: +234 806 707 3636
Email: stephenjenekwu@gmail.com

Abstract

The paper examined criminal profiling and the challenges of criminal investigation among the Nigeria Police Force. The specific objectives of the paper includes examining the mechanisms put in place to aid criminal profiling in the Nigerian criminal justice system, an evaluation of the effectiveness of the mechanisms; identification of the challenges facing criminal profiling in the Nigerian criminal justice; and suggestions on how criminal profiling can be effective in the Nigerian criminal justice system. Biological Theory of Crime was adopted as a choice of framework to buttress the paper. Arising from the secondary sources of data reviewed, the paper revealed that the establishment of a police records management system, a forensic laboratory system where evidence from DNA sources is scientifically examined, and a central database for all Nigerians were the mechanisms put in place to aid criminal profiling in Nigeria. It was also discovered that criminal investigative analysis, behavioural evidence approach, and environmental psychology were approaches to profiling criminals. The paper also established that the mechanisms and approaches used for criminal profiling in Nigeria were very relevant to the criminal justice system but appeared to be ineffective, resulting from inherent challenges such as bribery and corruption, computer illiteracy, lack of professionalism, inadequate funding and remuneration of police personnel and uncooperative attitudes of the members of the public, among others. It was recommended that professional psychologists should be recruited and form a separate department in the Nigeria Police Force; the police should be well funded and better remunerated to boost their morale and commitment to profiling, among others.

KEYWORDS: Crime, Criminal Profiling, Criminal Investigations, Nigeria Police Force.

Background

Criminal profiling involves determining an offender's personality qualities, behavioural patterns, locations, and demographic or biological features based on the elements of the crime (Edero, 2020). The concept of criminal profiling, according to the Federal Bureau of Investigations (FBI) of the United States, is a method for locating the perpetrator of a violent crime by determining the offender's personality and behavioural traits based on an examination of the crime that was committed (FIB, 2008). A particular offender may be connected to several crimes, and the profile may be used to forecast the identified offender's future behaviour.

Since the late 1990s, research findings have been published to support the application of criminal profiling to arson and later terrorism in the year 2000 and burglary in 2017. Prior to this, many criminal profiling researchers, including Kocsis (2013), Alison et al., (2010), and Ainsworth (2001), believed that criminal profiling was only relevant to sex related crimes, such as serial rape or sexual homicide (Beauregard & Field, 2018 Cited in Binti et al., 2022). Nigeria is one of the countries where criminal profiling is a relatively new enforcement method because it only began in the last two decades and is still a very contentious technique (Muhammad, 2022). Although many people have no idea what criminal profiling is or how it is done, it has nonetheless ingrained itself into the collective consciousness of people. This ignorance is equally as widespread among professionals as it is with the general population.

Despite the fact that criminal profiling is frequently used in investigations into serial crime and criminal behaviour, scholars almost universally agree that it lacks a scientific foundation and relies on subpar methodology. As a result, the reliability and usefulness of criminal profiling are seriously questioned, to the point where evidence cannot be utilized in court and grave injustices are brought about. Profilers are often portrayed as social outcasts who are very upset by how well they understand the minds of the unknown criminals they are looking for (Turvey, 2001). Criminal profiling is a topic that is not foreign to the society. Numerous understudies are already hard at work right now as a result of criminal psychology's constant media appearances. It is now common to hear about murderers and criminals who murder, rape, or assault victims because they have certain characteristics in common with the victims or because of certain twisted motives or goals. This information can be found in the news, online, and even in a number of documentaries (Edero, 2020).

Many serial killers and violent criminals suffer from psychiatric disorders brought on by strange past experiences that drive them to seek revenge on those who resemble those who have wronged them in the past or simply out of pure perverse delight. It is more challenging for the law enforcement agencies to apprehend criminals in these crimes since they are carried out in odd ways and there is little or no physical evidence connecting the criminals to the act. Over the years, forensic psychologists and analysts have tried to find out ways to identify these criminals based on how they work, how they act, who they want to hurt, and what they left behind at crime scenes (Beauregard & Field, 2018).

Based on their diverse backgrounds, different scholars have viewed criminal profiling in different ways. As a result, it has been given many different names, including criminal personality profiling, criminological profiling, behavioural profiling, criminal investigative analysis, offender profiling, psychological profiling, crime scene analysis, socio-psychological profiling, and linkage analysis (Labuschagne, 2006). Despite having various titles, these strategies all have the same objective, which is to assist detectives in using data from crime scenes and victim and witness narratives to create an offender description. Holmes (2000), in his own position opines that the main goal of profiling is to help find out criminals by extrapolating their personal characteristics from information about crimes.

In order to provide a multi-dimensional report, the psychology-trained professionals must draw on their understanding of human motivation, behaviour, and patterns. It does not reveal the precise name of the criminal, but by focusing on a few behavioural and personality traits, it suggests the type of

person who is most likely to have committed the crime. Ideas from brainstorming sessions with forensic experts and police detectives should include things like evidence from the crime scene (like blood stains), witness statements, autopsy results, photographs, and other related things like cameras found at the crime scene, weapons, and things used to torture people.

Both tangible and intangible tools are used to create criminal profiles. The crime scene, the offender's modus operandi (method of operation), his signature behaviour, any indications the perpetrator may have left behind while committing the crime, any indication that more than one person may have been engaged in the crime, and victimology are examples of tangible tools. The amount of planning that went into the crime, the level of control the offender had, the rise in emotion at the scene, the riskiness of both the offender and the victim, and the way the crime scene looked (disorganized versus organized) are all things that can be used to figure out the offender's personality. The profiler's intuition, expertise, and experience are among the intangible tools, as are their unusual ability to objectively enter the criminal's head and think like that person, as well as their analytical mind. This method might be referred to as a "paper tiger." It can be harmful by leading investigators astray or extremely helpful in assisting forensic scientists in focusing on an investigation. At best, it can be used as a way to work together and as a guide for a complete forensic and criminal investigation (Ronald, 2008).

It is not unexpected that the absence of forensic science and technological expertise as a tool for criminal profiling has not been addressed in the literature on Nigerian police concerns. A survey of the literature revealed that few studies had either a partial or complete focus on criminal profiling (forensic investigation) inside the Nigeria Police, despite the necessity for research on forensic technology. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, the majority of studies have focused on the need for police reforms rather than the necessity for criminal profiling and the obstacles to its efficacy. As a result, this study seeks to fill this gap in the literature and add to the body of knowledge. The establishment of a forensic laboratory and digital resource centre in Abuja by the Nigerian Police Force in 2016; the facility, which includes technologies for identifying crime suspects through features like Iris and facial recognition, potential identification marks, multiple and extended fingerprints, among others, are intended to aid the activities of its criminal intelligence and investigation department.

The Nigerian criminal justice system, in particular the Nigerian Police Force, is aware of the benefits and challenges of criminal profiling as a technique in criminal investigations. However, due to the inherent difficulties facing Nigeria Police Force, criminal profiling in Nigeria has not yet gained the degree of acceptance, usability, or institutionalization that it has in other jurisdictions. Hence, the focus of this paper was on Nigeria's criminal justice system especially Nigeria Police Force to examine criminal profiling and the problems it faces.

Statement of the Problem

The Nigeria Police Force (NPF) is charged with the responsibility of maintaining law and order and internal security, especially as they affect protection of lives and property of the entire populace (Nte et al., 2019). However, effort of the police in criminal investigations and protecting lives and property has been quite inadequate. The reasons are not far-fetched. They have to do with scanty numbers of trained personnel to manage criminal profiling tools such as the bio-data databases of Nigerians, Automated Fingerprint Identification System (AFIS), Deoxyribonucleic Acid (DNA) databases or equipment, and inadequate modern technological infrastructure that are used in investigating violent crimes like rape, assault, battery, terrorism, arson, domestic violence, gang violence, and kidnapping. It is argued that the absence or obsolete condition of these equipment may have rendered criminal profiling ineffective in Nigeria Police Force (NPF) (Muhammad, 2022). The consequences of these are numerous. Many violent crimes are on the rise daily in our society with the perpetrators undetected and so the protection of people's lives and property as well as Nigeria's social stability are now in great doubt due to the country's recent spike in violent crimes. The most serious violent

crimes, which have been on the rise lately, include cases of traditional crimes like armed robberies, arsons, murder, kidnapping, rape, hired assassinations, thuggery, and ritual killings among others (Edero, 2020). In the absence of effective criminal profiling tools, many innocent Nigerian may have been wrongly accused, while many criminals have escaped punishment because there was no forensic connection to the crimes to convict or exonerate them.

As Nte, et al (2019) asserted, a developed and reliable database for criminal profiling will help in linking several crime scenes together, exonerate the innocent (prisons in Nigeria will be decongested for once because many in there might have been wrongly detained), identify potential serial offenders, unravelling clues from old cases, comprehensively closing the unsolved cases and identifying the unknown perpetrators from numerous cases of only victims and not suspects, among other relevance of criminal profiling in criminal investigation. The Nigeria Police have faced inherent problems for decades, which have repeatedly thwarted reform efforts. One of the biggest issues is poor forensic analysis, which is frequently brought on by a lack of the necessary tools. To avert the grave consequences of the above-mentioned challenges, it needs to be fixed in order for the police to meet international standards like the Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) of the United States of America and other Western Nation which have extensively used criminal profiling in their efforts to combat crime.

The traditional eyewitness account and confession methods of criminal investigation used by Nigerian law enforcement agencies have been shown to be antiquated and out-of-date. In order to stop these sophisticated crimes, sophisticated tools like forensic science are required. This study makes the assertion that the most significant and pressing issue the Nigerian police are currently facing is their inability to involve proper criminal profiling techniques in criminal investigation and trials. In many cases, a lack of forensic investigation expertise may have resulted in the wrong people being investigated based on false informants, bad snitches, shoddy evidence gathering, and false confessions or false admissions.

A critical review of previous research efforts on criminal investigations in Nigeria shows that much of the efforts of such researchers had focused on the use of non-scientific tools of criminal investigations such as eyewitness testimony and statements of confessions, without any attention paid to the scientific approach of criminal profiling and the challenges hindering effective utilization of criminal investigation especially in Kogi State Police Command. The foregoing no doubt leaves a yawning gap in research that needs to be closed. Hence, the need for this current study to bridge the gap in the body of knowledge.

Olashile (2009) has also argued that the police records system is not based on strong forensic evidence. The implication here is that they are largely inadequate, and many criminals may easily escape detection because names, faces, and other physical body attributes, phone numbers and at times addresses change every day. This situation has created a challenge in criminal investigation landscape in Nigeria. Therefore, in the light of the foregoing, this paper sought to examine criminal profiling and the challenges of criminal investigation in Nigeria Police Force.

Aim and Objectives

The aim of this paper was to examine criminal profiling and challenges of criminal investigation in Nigerian Police Force. The specific objectives include to:

- a) Identify the mechanism to effective criminal profiling in Nigeria Police Force.
- b) Examine the effectiveness of the mechanisms used for criminal profiling in Nigeria Police Force..
- c) Identify the challenges to effective criminal profiling in Nigeria Police Force..

Methodology

Secondary sources of data collection was utilized for this paper including textbooks, journals and articles written by leading authors and scholars in the area of criminal profiling among other online articles, journals, abstracts, documentaries and books etc. which also served as secondary information source in this paper, were systematically reviewed and content analyzed base on the aim and objectives of the paper.

Theoretical Framework: Biological Theory of Crime

The Italian criminologist Cesare Lombroso's research from the nineteenth century is where the biological explanation of crime first emerged. Cesare Lombroso is known for his "born criminal" theory, which was the most common way to think about criminal behaviour in the late 19th century and early 20th century.

Lombroso essentially held that criminality was hereditary and that physical flaws could be used to identify criminals and establish their atavistic or primitive nature. For instance, the expressive face, manual dexterity, and small, roving eyes of a burglar could be used to identify him. Rapists had "jug ears," while habitual murderers had cold, glassy glances, bloodshot eyes, and large hawk-like nostrils. Lombroso, however, did not limit his opinions to male criminals; he co-wrote his first book to investigate the causes of female crime and came to the following conclusions about them: female criminals were far more ruthless than male criminals; they tended to be lustful and immodest; they were shorter and more wrinkled; they had darker hair and smaller skulls than "normal" women. However, Lombroso noted that there was less baldness among them. Women who committed crimes out of passion were more evil than men and had large lower jaws (Canter et al., 2006).

Based on the ideas of biological determinism, Lombroso's work on the identification and categorization of criminal "types" suggested that some people were born with characteristics that made them more likely to commit crimes. Lombroso not only felt that people were biologically predisposed to either criminal or law-abiding behaviour; he also thought that the type of crime that each individual criminal was biologically predisposed to committing could be identified by how they looked (Canter, 2006). Based on Darwin's theory of evolution, Lombroso claimed that there were three basic categories of criminals: criminals who were born criminals, criminals who were insane, and criminaloids.

He asserted that criminality is inherited and can be distinguished by bodily flaws, and that there is a born criminal. He sees specific physiognomic defects in criminals. He viewed criminals as brutal and primitive. These born criminals were inferior evolutionary reversioners in terms of their physical traits; they were degenerated, primordial criminals. According to Lombroso, born criminals are atavistic replicas of not only savage men but also the most vicious predators and rodents. This was stated in his magnum opus, *Criminal Man*. Since these creatures are not of our species but rather the species of blood-hungry beasts, this finding should not increase our sympathy for people who commit crimes from birth (as some argue). Instead, it should protect us against sympathy (Lombroso, 1986). In his thesis on criminal anthropology, he compared the skulls of executed and living criminals to those of apes and ancient humans and came to the conclusion that criminals were atavism victims. According to him, "born criminals" have 18 physical traits, provided that at least five of them are present. According to Lombroso (1986), these bodily traits/deformities consist of the following: the face's asymmetry abnormalities, deformities of the eye, excessively large cheekbones, and jawbones. Very large ears, occasionally very small ears, or ears that protrude from the head, like chimpanzees' do. Thieves may have a twisted, inverted, or flattened nose, while murderers may have an aquiline or beak-like nose or one with a tip that rises like a peak from enlarged nostrils. Lips that are thick, bulging, and protrude into the pelvic organs are an inversion of sex traits. Extra-long arms and extra fingers are just two examples.

According to Lombroso, criminals who were mad were those who had mental diseases as well as some physical defects (Lombroso, 1876). The criminaloids were a sizable broad class of criminals without any distinguishing traits. They did not have any observable mental disorders, but their emotional and mental makeup made them more likely to engage in criminal behaviour in specific situations, such as when there were opportunities to do so (Turvey, 2011). This classification has been contrasted with the later clinical diagnosis of psychopathic personality disorder. Lombroso argued that criminaloids are typically left-handed, which he claimed was typical of con artists. He also said that they often lose their hair and turn grey early, don't feel pain, and drink a lot. The theory has been criticised that it is incorrect and that there is no such thing as a physically defined criminal type.

The Relevance of Biological Theory of Crime to Criminal Profiling

The idea is extremely relevant to the art and science of criminal profiling, since Lombroso adhered to the biological idea, he thought that criminals had distinguishable characteristics. If those traits can be identified, professionals in the criminal justice and law enforcement systems, particularly those from the Nigeria Police Force, may be able to use them to identify potential criminals and those responsible for specific crimes in Nigeria. Furthermore, if those quirks could be discovered, they could be able to anticipate or even stop illegal behaviour.

Literature Review

This involves the review of books, reports, publications, newspapers, magazines, academic journal articles, archival materials, and internet-based documented source materials, among others, that are pertinent to this paper is thus a part of the literature review process. Because of this, the aim and objectives of the paper were used to evaluate the review of relevant and related literature.

Conceptual Review

The following concepts are explained in the paper from the perspectives of different scholars. Thus:

Criminal profiling

Criminal profiling is the process of extrapolating an offender's traits from his or her behaviour at the crime scene. Criminal profiling, according to Douglas and Burgess (1996), is the process of conducting an investigation using information that is readily available about a crime and the crime scene to create a psychosomatic representation of the known or suspected criminal mastermind (Douglas & Burgess, 1996, cited in Muller, 2000:235). For instance, a profiler would try to determine a criminal's age, gender, or employment history based on how they behaved during the time the crime was committed. This procedure has been referred to as "offender profiling," "psychological profiling," and "specific profile analysis. Criminal profiling is frequently applied to serious sorts of crime, such as murder or rape, as well as to incidents when the identity of the culprit is unknown. Another task that profilers are likely to focus on (Bull et al., 2006) is collecting crimes series, which are collections of crimes believed to have been perpetrated by the same criminal.

Criminal investigation

Criminal investigation is an applied science that involves the study of facts, used to identify, locate and prove the guilt of an accused criminal. Criminal investigation is concerned with activities that violate the law of the state legal system that regards such violation as serious enough to necessitate the need for investigations. A complete criminal investigation can include searching, interviews, interrogations, evidence collection and preservation and various methods of investigation. Modern-day criminal investigations commonly employ many modern scientific techniques known collectively as forensic science (Sylvester & Agbeyi, 2019). Criminal investigation according to these authors refers to the process of collecting information (or evidence) about a crime in order to: (i) Determine if

a crime has been committed. (ii) Identify the perpetrator. (iii) Apprehend the perpetrator. (iv) Provide evidence to support a conviction in court.

Criminal Justice System

A criminal justice system is a collection of governmental and non-governmental organizations that are responsible for upholding the criminal code in accordance with established procedural guidelines and constraints. A system or a procedure may be used to define criminal justice. As a system, it is made up of three sub-systems or components: the police, the courts, and corrections. The police, the courts, and corrections are in charge of enforcing the law. Examples of these courts include trial and appellate courts; offices of the prosecutor and public defender; probation and parole offices; and custodial institutions (jails, prisons, reformatories, half-way houses, etc. responsible for some or all probation, parole, and custodial functions). Additionally, a sentencing guidelines commission exists in some jurisdictions (Iwerimie-Jaja, 2003).

The historical to modern development of criminal profiling

Criminal profilers and criminal psychologists have held a variety of divergent opinions regarding the historical event that is credited with being the catalyst for the first application of profiling offenders based on their behavioural and psychological traits. In the past, investigators who worked for different governments or religions often used profiles and profiling to make a bad name for a certain group. As a result, there has been bloodshed and ignorance (Woodworth & Porter, 2001).

Nevertheless, informal criminal profiling has a lengthy history that dates to the 1880s, when crime scene evidence was utilized to forecast the characteristics of British serial killer Jack the Ripper (Turvey, 2011). Although there have been improvements over time, prior work in profiling was still mainly reliant on experience and unofficial research until recently, which sparked a discussion about the veracity of criminal profiling (Turvey, 2011). In order to identify the type of perpetrator who might have committed the crime and to fill in information gaps, modern criminal profiling is the science of gathering information about an offender's personality traits, behavioural tendencies, geographic location, and demographic or biological descriptors (Kocsis, 2013). It has psychological, criminological, and forensic scientific roots (Turvey, 2011).

Approaches put in place by the Nigeria Police Force (NPF) to help Criminal Profiling.

The Nigerian government has established the following mechanisms to help in the process of conducting criminal profiling. According to Abubakar and Bashir (2017), profiling seeks to help to find those responsible for committing specific crimes and engaging in criminal behaviour, hence the authors highlighted the following approaches set up to aid profiling in Nigeria:

Forensic laboratory in Nigeria:

The only forensic laboratories used by the Nigerian government are the new one, which the Lagos State Government recently inaugurated, and the two older ones, one in Abuja and one in Oshodi, Lagos. The Forensic Section is a professional/specialist arm of the Nigerian Police that provides support to investigators both inside and outside the Force. At the Force CIID Annex in Lagos, the Section's Forensic Laboratory is staffed by a Commissioner of Police for Forensics and eighteen other officers. Twenty-Nine (29) additional officers and a Commissioner of Police Forensic serve in the Abuja Head Office. According to the Department of ICT, Nigeria Police Force (2020), the following units make up the Section, with most of them performing their duties in Lagos and a few in Abuja

Automated Fingerprint Identification System (AFIS) Unit:

In Lagos, the CCR's manual records are converted to digital format by the AFIS unit for suspect enrolment and profiling. For the purpose of capturing suspects, the FCIID in Abuja has installed a

biometric system. In accordance with the Inspector General Police's approval, six (6) Biometric systems were also deployed to the six geopolitical zones of Maiduguri, Kano, FCT, Awka, Lagos, and Port Harcourt (Abubakar & Bashir, 2017). Additionally, Muhammad (2022) posited that this unit transports the fingerprints of nominees, appointees, and job- and visa-seekers to Lagos' Central Criminal Registry (CCR) so that they can be cleared and issued Character Certificates. The section in charge of forensic examination and analysis of contested documents, forgery, handwriting, and signatures is known as the "Document Unit." Ten (10) employees are being trained by one of the retired specialists.

The Ballistic Unit:

This unit examines, analyzes, and compiles reports on the investigational firearms and ammunition (Muhammad, 2022).

The Crime Scene Management Unit:

This unit assists IPOs in processing a crime scene, gathering, preserving, and packaging exhibits for investigation, analysis, and reporting. This unit responds to requests from Sectional Heads, State CIIDs, Divisional Headquarters, and other security agencies. Including expressing an expert opinion on the manner in which a crime is committed. Muhammad (2022), opined that the analysis and detection of chemical components in poison, contaminated goods, and gun powder are the topics covered in the chemistry/toxicology unit.

The Serology/DNA unit:

This unit analyzes suspected blood stains to determine whether they are real blood or human blood. Since 2010, it has educated and qualified 3 DNA Examiners. All electronic devices with storage capabilities can be used for digital analysis with our Cellebrite UFED Machine. Abubakar and Bashir (2017) postulated that the machine has the ability to recover deleted contents from such devices, which can be useful in ongoing investigations in which the device is an exhibit. It has one officer who was certified by UNODC after receiving training in Kenya, two Cellebrite UFED machines that were donated to the NPF, one of which is located in the AFIS unit on the second floor of FHQ Abuja, and the other of which was deployed to Maiduguri by the certified officer, who also trained three additional officers to operate the machine, all of whom are now operational. When necessary, Certified Experts in each of these areas are readily available to provide expert testimony in court (Abubakar& Bashir, 2017).

Criminal profiling appears to be ineffective in the Nigerian criminal justice system since these resources are not being fully utilized perhaps, due to lack of technological know-how among other inherent challenges.

Software for the Police Records Management System (RMS):

Police records management systems (RMS) allow law enforcement agencies to store, retrieve, maintain, archive, and examine data, records, or files related to law enforcement operations, according to Best Police Management System (2020). These tools automate essential tasks that improve daily operations.

Police RMS solutions oversee the creation of records from the time they are first generated to the point of completion. These solutions include standard documents like investigation reports, 911/CAD reports, booking and arrest reports, criminal identification, detention records, and citations and tickets. For law enforcement employee operations, these solutions might also offer capability for managing personnel files and other administrative paperwork. These instruments are used by law enforcement personnel to record data that serves as proof of alleged or established criminal activity (Muhammed, 2022).

Strong police RMS tools may include fundamental elements for managing evidence, or they may integrate directly with specialized systems that do so. The effectiveness of investigating crimes is increased by the fact that many of these solutions support agency-to-agency data sharing to communicate multi-jurisdictional information on people, organizations, locations, and vehicle items. Police officers may now follow activities while on the move thanks to mobile record generation and storage offered by modern police RMS solutions. Additionally, it is typical for these tools to have access to car plate recognition, master person indices, and public national registries for sex offenders. They also typically feature a public portal where users may obtain crime-related data that is populated from databases (Edero, 2020).

As highlighted by Edero (2020) the following requirements must be met for a product to be eligible for inclusion in the Police Records Management System category: It must permit law enforcement organizations to record important data and records related to incident reporting. Support storing a variety of records, such as citations, warrants, arrest reports, incident reports, and field interviews, among others.

The Nigerian population's central data base:

A network's centralized database often stores data or information in a specific place. It enables the gathering and storage of data from current databases in a single database for sharing, analysis, and updating within an organization. In order for criminal profiling to be successful in Nigeria, the amount of data that businesses and government institutions typically collect and maintain must be managed in a more effective and efficient manner (Muhammed, 2022). In Nigeria, organizations and government institutions now distribute data in a redundant and inconsistent manner on numerous levels. Numerous organizations, including the Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC), the Nigerian Communication Commission (NCC), the National Identity Management Commission (NIMC), and banks, among others, gather essentially the same information from people (Abubakar & Bashir, 2017).

For instance, the NCC ordered all cell companies to gather subscriber information, including biometric information. Similar to this, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) ordered all banks to comply with the Bank Verification Number (BVN) exercise so that client bank information, including their biometric, will be linked together and CBN may regulate customer bank accounts using unique number identification (i.e. BVN). In addition to providing licenses, FRSC also recorded driver information and biometrics during the exercise and stored them in their database. The Nigerian Immigration Service (NIS) also recorded the biometric information and data of citizens requesting an international passport. National Identity Numbers (NINs) and Cards are being issued to residents by NIMC as of late. Biometric information about the citizens is collected and kept in their database. The currently suggested framework and architecture are displayed in the following figures:

Effectiveness of Criminal Profiling in Nigerian Criminal Justice System Especially Nigeria Police Force Kogi State Command

The usefulness and even the legitimacy of criminal profiling have been contested. Some detractors only contest the accuracy of criminal profiles. Others wonder if we ought to concentrate on the individuals (violent and sexual offenders) rather than the acts (violent and sexual offences). According to this theory, focusing on individuals fosters the problematic notion of "dangerous individuals" (Edero, 2020).

Research shows that Nigeria's top law enforcement and security agency, the Nigeria Police Force, doesn't have the most up-to-date technology in its forensic laboratory (Evelyn, 2021). Criminal investigation is a significant issue for Nigerian policing as claimed by Evelyn (2021). The advancement of forensic technology has made the biggest contributions to criminal investigation. The Nigerian case is a failure, despite the fact that forensic investigation has successfully solved millions of crimes in developed nations like the U.S. and the UK. It is well known that the Nigerian police's centralized way of doing things gives the federal government a lot of power and may cause it to get involved in local affairs, which could mean there isn't enough money for forensic technology equipment for investigations.

Challenges to the Effectiveness of Criminal Profiling in the Criminal Justice System - Nigeria Police Force

Profiling violent crimes presents a variety of difficulties for law enforcement agencies, particularly the Nigeria Police Force. These difficulties range from technical to structural, and occasionally they relate to the ability of the individual enforcers to process crucial information. Therefore, it is essential to comprehend these obstacles in order to develop workable solutions when such difficulties arise. The following are what they are:

Information Overload

"Intelligence overload" is another information-related hurdle. This happens when a single enforcement agency is unable to efficiently filter the raw data, which leads to an abundance of data clogging the inquiry. The "noise" problem is connected to this challenge. Again, this problem could be lessened if there was good technical and systemic integration between the enforcement divisions (Holmes, 2000).

Even though the aforementioned issues are amply supported by official documentation and academic research, in addition to news reports from the day-to-day media, it is not necessary to "prove" in this paper that Nigeria's criminal justice system falls short of international norms when it comes to criminal profiling, particularly with regard to the Nigeria Police Force. Instead, what is required is the identification of the primary deficiencies, issues, and challenges that are to blame for the state of affairs (Sylvester & Agbeyi, 2019). In Nigeria's justice system, a number of issues have been identified as obstacles or barriers to efficient criminal profiling. Among these factors are those emphasized and critically explored below.

Insufficient funding

The main barriers that have historically prevented spending on preventing crime from being channelled into building up criminal justice systems are a lack of money and inadequate funding (Alemika & Chukwuma, 1990). According to the United Nations Department of Public Information (2000) money is still urgently needed for future research despite investment in community and situation prevention rising over the previous two decades and subjects like child development beginning to draw greater focus. To adapt crime control and preventive strategies to increasingly

modern crimes, such as organized and multinational crimes, funding will be required (Alemika & Chukwuma, 1990). As trade and commerce become more global, business and leisure travel expand, and traditional borders open up, the current levels of these offenses could skyrocket.

The Nigerian Police's Type of Training and Qualifications

Due to the nature of their training, many police officers, including criminal profilers, spend most of their time performing monotonous, repetitive tasks like filling out paperwork and waiting for events to occur. They are rarely involved in resolving crisis situations (Tamuno, 1970). The Nigerian police force is unable to reduce crime rates due to a lack of experienced and trained personnel. According to Alemika (1999), many police departments failed to emphasize during recruitment the qualities necessary for policing, such as a high level of intelligence, education, tact, sound judgment, physical courage, emotional stability, impartiality, and honesty, which are typically lacking in police officers during their time on duty due to insufficient education during training and recruitment. A 1995 study that compared 1993 to 1990 in United States statistics indicated that twice as many police agencies needed officers to have some college education, with 8% requiring some kind of degree and 1% requiring a four-year degree, demonstrating the growing emphasis on the necessity for police education (Alemika, 1999).

Lack of adequate Manpower in the Nigerian Police Force

It is well known that the Nigerian police force consistently lacks manpower in a number of important sectors. For instance, the force's overall size was 143,204 in 1993 (Annual Report of the NPF, 1993:3). The Nigerian police population ratio was 1:618 in 1991, when the nation's population was 83.5 million. The United Nations recommends one police officer for every 400 people, which falls short of this. A position of one police officer for every 400 people has been established in several western nations (including the United States, Britain, France, and others) as being necessary for improved crime control (Chifflet, 2015).

It is undisputed, according to the author, (Chifflet, 2015), that the Nigerian police force is understaffed. The workers at different police stations are so overworked that concerns are frequently politely rejected by citing a lack of staff as a handy excuse for the inability to respond promptly or effectively. Not only does the Nigerian police force lack personnel, but it also lacks qualified personnel.

Lack of Adequate Equipment

In order to effectively combat crime, Odekunle (2004) contends that walkie-talkies, radios, and telephones are essential tools. Radios and walkie-talkies are typically broken or even unusable where they are present. According to Odekunle (2004), the Nigerian police force is in need of more vehicles, especially quick-moving, reliable patrol cars. As a result, they rarely pursue criminals in hot pursuit.

Rogers (2003) asserts that it is a well-known fact that dangerous criminals, such as armed robbers, have significantly better weapons than the police. While the majority of armed robbers typically carry high-tech automatic guns, there aren't many armed police officers. Their most popular weapons are the short rifle and the Mark IV rifle, both of which are difficult to carry and wield. Most police officers carry truncheons and batons, which don't work against criminals or other troublemakers.

Corruption

The Nigerian legal system has a number of major issues that work against socioeconomic growth, one of which is corruption (Cohen, 2013). As strong and well-placed Nigerians vie to outdo one another in the expropriation of the so-called "National Cake," corruption is pervasive and has practically become

institutionalized (Cohen, 2013). According to Bloom (2013), the police are not immune from corruption, because they are an integral component of Nigerian society. Balogun (2013) asserts that extortion of meagre sums of money, or what one may refer to as "peanut money," from operators of commercial vehicles and traffic infractions is a prevalent kind of police corruption. This is not really a big deal to us. Our main worry is that police corruption, no matter how much of it there is, encourages and facilitates rather than deters criminal activity in our nation (Balogun, 2013).

The Nigeria Police Force has a high incidence of corruption and extortion. The reputation of the police has been severely tarnished by this behaviour (Neild, 2007). Asserting that police corruption is a severe problem because they are expected to be morally honest as law enforcement officers, Alemika (1999) agrees with Neild. Society is in danger if the police, who are tasked with stopping and detecting crime and corruption and prosecuting offenders, are corrupt themselves. The police also possess authority that has a significant impact on residents' lives, property, and safety. Citizens feel unsafe where such power is tainted by corrupt tendencies. Extortion, a type of robbery, is another manifestation of this corruption (Neild, 2007). Police corruption explains why such activities endanger the public and why the police are therefore unable to live up to expectations. Alemika (1999) asserts that police brutality is frequently used as a tactic for pressuring people to give in to demands for bribes and that it occasionally serves as a form of punishment for refusing to comply with the police's demands for satisfaction.

Integrity is lacking.

Eigege (2006) asserts that one of the core values of public officials is integrity. It directs how one behaves while fulfilling official obligations. For instance, the Nigerian Police Force lacks integrity. The officers frequently display their lack of professionalism and extreme unreliability by taking part in criminal activity or collaborating with offenders. They frequently defend the wealthy in their daily work. Their position is frequently utilized to intimidate, extort, and bribe their fellow residents. This was also expressed by Dauda (2008): "The police, in my opinion, are a shame to Nigerians; they conduct awful things... Consider the scenario where cops kill an innocent individual and then claim the next day that he was caught stealing.

Police abuse and harassment of defenceless people

These are additional significant barriers that stand in the Nigeria Police's way of ensuring the safety of people and their property as well as the maintenance of law and order. Ismail (2008) asserts that the police frequently break the law with the support of dictatorial governments and oppressive policies. Most of the time, police have acted as if they were the law, killing innocent people and arbitrarily detaining others without consequence. Political opponents of governments, workers, radicalized students, and human rights activists have always been subjected to disproportionately high rates of police brutality, kidnappings, unlawful searches and seizures, invasions of privacy, extrajudicial killings, bodily harm, intimidation, and harassment, as well as loss of personal freedoms (Alemika, 1993:208).

Empirical Review

Muhammad (2022) examined the factors that could challenge databases and affect the realization of the benefits of forensic intelligence in Nigeria. The study was carried out among the Criminal Investigations and Intelligence Departments (CIIDs) in Zone 1 of the Nigeria Police. The respondents were, the Investigating Police Officers (IPOs) serving in the zone's CIIDs. Zone 1 is one of the twelve zonal police commands in Nigeria, comprising of the zonal command headquarters and three state commands, that is, Kano, Jigawa, and Katsina states. Out of the total population of 3,503, a sample size of 347 was determined using Krejcie and Morgan's table of sample size estimation. Using survey method, and with police investigators as respondents, seven challenges were determined, and hypotheses were tested to find out if the challenges have a significant association among themselves.

Of the variables (that is, the seven challenges), three (corruption, lack of interagency cooperation, and undue interference in investigations) indicate statistically significant association with unreliable databases. The study recommended that authorities should address the challenges to ensure reliable databases and effective forensic intelligence for the police to utilize.

Nwokolo and Ivongbe (2022) examined forensic science evidence admissibility as an instrument for handling criminal prosecution in the process of justice. It was conducted by empirically reviewing related literature in the field of Forensic Science using a qualitative research method and survey research design. The paper used interview sessions to generate primary data and compared the result with the secondary data to justify the relationship of Forensic Science evidence admissibility. The researchers comparatively analysed the importance of Forensic Science evidence in administering justice during criminal proceedings using applicable case studies. The research findings revealed that proper Forensic Science evidence are used to grant justice as it is a scientific method of justifying truth in a criminal investigation and prosecution both in the court of law and law enforcement agency office. The study concluded and recommended among others that Forensic Science should be included as an academic discipline in higher institutions in Nigeria, particularly in Nigeria Police Colleges and Law Schools where proper techniques and their application should be taught in grooming more Forensic Experts. The paper also recommended and stressed the need to establish more forensic laboratories in Nigeria with proper funding as well as the enactment of a law for the admissibility of forensic evidence in the court of law.

Meanwhile, the study ignored the challenges that may impede the effectiveness of forensic science in criminal investigation hence, the current paper unveiled such challenges to bridge the gap in this prior existing research.

Ibrahim and Andrew (2021) examined prevalence of psychopathy among criminal and non-criminal population in Kaduna State Nigeria. Survey method was used to study the participants comprising of both males and females in Kaduna North Local Government area of Kaduna state using Krejcie and Morgan formula to determine the sample size of 384. An adopted standardized instrument of Hare Psychopathic Checklist Revised (PCL-R) 2nd edition was used to collect the data. Four research hypotheses were tested. And cognitive perspective theory was adopted in the study. The results revealed that the reliability statistics for the scale based on the total number of 20 items was .823 and considered to be highly significant. Criminal population respondent have highly prevalence rate of committing crime more than the non-committing crime more than the non-Criminal population in Kaduna state. Which indicate a mean score of 3.36 with a standard deviation of 497 of 192 Criminal population respondent have highly prevalence rate of committing crime in Kaduna state. While mean score of 2.91 with standard deviation of .422 of 192 non- Criminal population respondent have low prevalence rate of committing crime in Kaduna state. The study also found that empathy is an important factor to consider when investigating the construct of psychopathy. Hence, there is need to move away from focusing on behavioural correlates (antisocial and criminal behaviours), and to focus more on affective components and find ways to assess these affective constructs in a more valid and reliable manner.

The study unavoidably shied away from studying the real practice of criminal profiling which would have helped more in determining the prevalence of psychopathy among criminals and non-criminals in the study area. Hence, the current paper centred on criminal profiling.

Discussions

The paper examined criminal profiling and the challenges of criminal investigation in the Nigeria Police Force and based on the aim and objectives of the paper, the following are discussed:

The paper revealed in line with the publication of the Best Police Management System (2020), that police records management systems (RMS) enable law enforcement agencies to store, retrieve, retain,

archive, and view information, records, or files pertaining to law enforcement operations. These tools automate vital processes that enhance the day-to-day operations of criminal profiling.

The paper also revealed that the establishment of forensic laboratory system is another approach put in place to aid the practice of criminal profiling in the criminal investigation. In Nigeria, profilers such as Divisional Crime Officers (DCOs), Inspector Crime Officers (ICOs), and Investigative Crime Officers (ICOs) among the Nigeria Police Force take photographs and physical measurements of crime scenes, identify and collect forensic evidence, and maintain the proper chain of custody of that evidence. A typical example of modern forensics evidence is the use of DNA profiling. This is also true because crime scene investigators collect evidence from sources such as DNA, fingerprints, footprints, tire tracks, blood samples, other body fluids, hairs, semen, saliva, bone, fibres, and fire debris that can be detected and used for forensic purposes to track the right offender of a particular crime and criminal behaviour for justice to be served.

The paper further revealed in line with the publication of the Department of ICT, Nigeria Police Force (2020) that the forensic section is a professional/specialist arm of the Nigeria Police that renders support to investigators within and outside the Force. Hence, the following units were created, including the Automated Fingerprint Identification System (AFIS) Unit and the Document Unit. The Document Unit is in charge of forensic examination and analysis of disputed documents, forgery, handwriting, and signatures. The ballistics unit handles examination, analysis, and reporting on firearms and ammunition under investigation. The Crime Scene Management Unit assists IPO's to process a crime scene and collect, preserve, and package exhibits for examination, analysis, and reporting. The Chemistry/Toxicology Unit deals with analysis and detection of chemical components in gun powder, poison, adulterated products etc. The Serology/DNA Unit handles analysis of suspected blood stains to determine whether they are blood or human blood. The Digital Forensic Unit deals with all electronic devices and machines have the capacity to recall deleted files from such devices, which can help an ongoing investigation where the device is an exhibit.

The paper equally revealed that the central database for all Nigerians is another mechanism set up to profile criminals in the justice system. The centralized and computerized storage of Nigerians' profiles in a database, which constitutes an important investigative resource in contemporary criminal investigation in the Nigeria Police Force enables the systematic comparison and automated matching of crime scene samples and individual profiles. Bank verification number (BVN), national identity number (NIN), SIM card number registration details of the suspects, and driver's license, among other things, could be used to obtain the necessary information for criminal profiling in this regard. It was revealed that Abubakar and Bashir (2017) cited instances in Nigeria where the NCC directed all mobile operators to collect data about their subscribers, including biometric data. Similarly, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) directed all banks to comply with the Bank Verification Number (BVN) exercise so that customers bank details, including their biometrics, will be linked together and that, through that, CBN can have control over bank accounts of customers using unique number identification (i.e., BVN). FRSC also provided drivers with licenses. They captured details and biometrics of drivers during the exercise and stored them in their database. The Nigerian Immigration Service (NIS) also captured data and biometrics of citizens applying for international passports. NIMC has recently registered and is providing citizens with National Identity Numbers (NIN) and Cards. The citizens data, including biometrics, are captured and stored within their database as tools of profiling and easy tracking of crime perpetrators.

The paper established that the above mechanism set up to aid the practice of criminal profiling were very relevant to the criminal justice system in Nigeria, though the relevance of these approaches is subject to the optimal utilization of the modalities listed above. Meanwhile, the approaches have been effective in criminal profiling exercise but not at its optimal level, reasons not farfetched from the inherent challenges facing the Nigeria Police Force. This revelation from the reviews of literature is not shocking because the glaring menace of bribery and corruption has eaten deep into the fabric of all aspects of law enforcement agencies, including the criminal justice system, and the Nigeria Police

Force is not an exception. A situation whereby profilers receive what is popularly called "sorting money," a slang for bribery payment, to quench an investigation or be reluctant to profile properly is corruption, and it affects the criminal justice system. In light of these, scholars such as Uruena (2003), Alemika (1999), and Neild (2004), among others, who asserted that police corruption commonly involves paltry sums or what could be called "peanut money" extorted from suspects and other forms of corruption in the profession. The implication of this is that police corruption, regardless of the amount involved, promotes and facilitates, rather than checks, criminal activities in the country as the corruption of the police does not stop at the checkpoints; it affects criminal investigations and profiling.

The paper also revealed challenges such as lack of professionalism on the part of Police profilers as a factor hindering the effective outcome of criminal profiling, as it is no longer news that criminal profiling appears to be a professional exercise and the lack of technical know-how hinders the effective outcome of it. This could be true because, being an art and science, successful criminal profilers must possess excellent analytical and critical thinking abilities, good communication skills, quality training, sound professional qualifications, and the ability to effectively analyse scientific and statistical data. Hence, only professionals can handle it effectively and a lack of it is a challenge to its outcome. The position of scholars such as Alemika (1999) is relevant also as they postulated that during recruitment, many police departments did not focus on the qualities that are important to policing, such as a high degree of intelligence, education, tact, sound judgment, physical courage, emotional stability, impartiality, and honesty, which are generally lacking in their time of duty as a result of inadequate education during training and recruitment.

The paper also in tandem with the submissions of scholars such as Elgege (2006), Otuba and Coker (2006), among others established that in the Nigerian criminal justice system, when a crime is reported at a police station, the practice is for the complaint desk officer to request money to purchase stationery to record the complaint and open a file. Afterwards, where the need arises to visit the scene of the crime, the complainant must provide transportation, because there is usually no vehicle attached to the criminal investigations department. If the crime involves a murder, the complainant or the accused is called upon to pay for a post-mortem examination because funds are not available for such activities. When investigations have been completed, the complainant or the accused person is also called upon to provide funds for the duplication of the investigation case file. It is clear from the foregoing that criminal investigations and profiling are underfunded in Nigeria and that constitutes an obstacle to effective criminal profiling.

The theoretical framework adopted in this paper also justified the revelations from the reviews as Lombroso's work on the identification and categorization of criminal "types" suggested that some people were born with characteristics that made them more likely to commit crimes. People were biologically predisposed to criminal behaviour and the type of crime that each individual criminal was biologically predisposed to committing could be identified by how they looked (Canter et al., 2006). The criminaloids were a sizable broad class of criminals without any distinguishing traits. Criminals had distinguishable characteristics, and if those traits can be identified, professionals in the criminal investigation, particularly those from the Nigeria Police Force, may be able to use them to identify potential criminals and those responsible for specific crimes in Nigeria. Moreover, if those quirks could be discovered, they could be able to anticipate or even prevent anticipated criminal behaviours.

Conclusion

After a critical examination of the revelations of this paper, it can be safely concluded that criminal profiling is very relevant to the Nigeria Police Force but not effective and sufficiently reliable to be admissible in all cases. Because with profiling evidence, it is easier to prove innocence than guilt, but this does not mean that it is not reliable in some cases. And so, only the Divisional Crime Officers, Inspector Crime Officers, and Investigative Crime Officers can qualify as expert profilers, either by knowledge, skill, experience, training, or education, but criminal profiling, as we have seen, is

supposed to fall under a specialized field of knowledge. Profilers, who are supposed to be criminal investigators, have mostly taken on the role of criminal prosecutors among the Nigeria Police Force and this is one of the problems that makes it hard to know how reliable criminal profiling can be.

Recommendations

Based on the forgoing, the following recommendations were made:

- i. To have a reliable profiling outcome, profilers in the Nigeria Police Force should possess strong critical thinking skills using logic and reasoning, strong intuition and analytical skills, emotional detachment, and an understanding of criminal minds and psychology.
- ii. Government agencies and policies should entrench the central database for all Nigerians to enable quick tracking of criminals by profilers because sensitive information such as personal data is necessary for an effective and reliable outcome of criminal profiling.
- iii. Having discovered that lack of professionalism is a challenge to effective criminal profiling, NPF should create an offender profiling department different from the Criminal Investigation/Intelligence Department (CIID) and recruit trained psychologists who are professionals with appropriate skills and expertise in the area, because if profiling is being handled by such experts, then the outcome would be more reliable.
- iv. The police should be well remunerated to boost their morale, increase their motivation and enthusiasm to utilize with dedication the apparatus for profiling. They need better funding as well, in order to procure the necessary computer devices and gadgets, motor able vehicles, and forensic laboratory equipment to enhance their performance in profiling criminals. Similarly, police management should remind citizens of the importance of always cooperating and working with the police in order to provide adequate and timely information on the activities of suspected and even suspicious people in their neighbourhood.

REFERENCES

- Abubakar, M. & Bashir, M. S. (2017). Centralized Database: A prerequisite for security and Sustainable development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Computer Science and Technology (IJIRCST)* 5, (1), 2347-5552.
- Ainsworth, P. (2001). *Offender Profiling and Crime Analysis*, Devon Willian Publishing.
- Alison, L., Bennel, C., Ormerod, D., & Macros, A., (2002). The personality paradox in offender profiling. *Journal of Psychology, Public policy, and Law*, 8(1), 115-135.
- Alison, L., Goodwill, A., Almond, L., Van, C. & Winter, J. (2010). Pragmatic solutions to offender profiling and behavioural investigative advice. *Journal of Legal and Criminological Psychology*, 15(1), 115-132.
- Alemika, E. E. O. & Chukwuma, I. (2000). *Police community violence in Nigeria*. Centre for Law Enforcement Education.
- Alemika E. E. (1999). Policing and perceptions of police in Nigeria. *Police Studies* 1(4),161-176.
- Alemika, E. E. O. (1993). *Criminology, criminal justice and the philosophy of policing in T. N. Tamuno, I. L. Bashir, E .E. O Alemika and A. O. Akano (eds.) policing Nigeria: Past, Present and Future*. Malthouse Press Limited.

- Angela, N. T., Marcus, T. B. & Holly, A. M. (2007). Perceptions of the validity and utility of Criminal profiling among forensic psychologists and psychiatrists. An exploratory Internet survey. *Research and Practice* 2006 (1), 51– 58.
- Anyanabia, A., Eric, A. & Oluka, L. N. (2019). Forensic technology and crime management in Nigeria. A Study of Rivers State. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, (14).
- Asika, N. (2001). Research methodology in the behavioural sciences, Longman Publisher Ibadan, Nigeria. 39-40.
- Balogun, A. T. (2003). Crime control strategy. 8 Point Strategies of the Nigerian police force Programme action, to serve and to protect with Integrity: Yalian Press Ltd.
- Beaves, A. S., Loundsbury, J. K., Richards, S. W., Hick, G. J., Skolits, S. and Esquivel, S. L. (2013). Practical consideration for using exploratory factor analysis in educational research. *Practical Assessment Research Evaluation*, 18(1).
- Bennell, C. & Jones, N. J., (2005). Between a ROC and a Hard Place: A method for linking Serial burglaries by Modus Operandi. *Journal of Investigative Psychology and offender Profiling*, 23 -41.
- Best Police Management System, (2020). Public safety and law enforcement software. <https://www.g2.com/categories/police-records-management-system-rms#>
- Beauregard, E. & Field, J. (2018). Body disposal patterns of sexual murderers: Implications for Offender profiling. *Journal of Police and Criminal Psychology*, 23, 81-89.
- Blackburn, R. (1997). The psychology of criminal conduct: Theory, Research and Practice Wiley And Sons.
- Bloom, R. (2013). Foundations of psychological profiling. Boca Raton: CRC Press.; Canter, D. (1995). Psychology of offender profiling, 343-55 in R. Bull & D. Carson (eds) Handbook of Psychology in Legal Contexts. NY: Wiley.
- Binti, M. M., Said, M. H., Bin, M. A., Hassan, M. S., Rajamanickam, R. & Dahlan, N. K. (2022). Criminal Profiling: Then and Now: Prospect and Challenges in Malaysia. *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 11(1), 2022-0007
- Bull, R., Cooke, C., Hatcher, R., Woodhams, J., Bilby, C. & Grant, T. (2006). Criminal Psychology: Beginners Guides. Oxford: Oneworld.
- Clark, J., Boccaccini, M., Caillouet, B. & Chaplin, W. (2007). Five factor model or personality traits, jury selection, and case outcomes in criminal and civil cases. *Criminal Justice and Behavior*, 34, 641– 660.
- Canter, D. (2006). Offender profiling and investigative psychology. *Journal of Investigative Psychology and Offender Profiling*, 1(1), 1-15.

- Canter, D. (2000). Offender profiling and criminal differentiation. *Legal and criminological Psychology*.
- Chifflet, P. (2015). Questioning the validity of criminal profiling: An evidence-based approach. *Australian and New Zealand Journal of Criminology*, 48(2), 238-255.
- Chinwokwu, E. C. (2012). Crime and criminal investigation in Nigeria: A study of police criminal investigation in Enugu State. *African Journal of Law and Criminology* 2(1), 46-55.
- Clare, P. K. & Kramer, J. H. (1977). *Introduction to American corrections*, Boston, MA: Holbrook Press, Inc.
- Cohen L. (2013). *Research methods in education*, sixth edition - STIBA Malang. URL: www.stiba-malang.ac.id/.../RESEARCH%20METHOD%20COHEN%20ok.
- Copson, G. (1995). *Coals to Newcastle? Police use of offender profiling*. Police Research Group Special Interest Paper 7. London: Home Office.
- Dauda, M. (2008). Commenting on the helpless state of police when confronted with armed Robbers. *Tell magazine* May, 26th
- David, M. S., Abdullahi, I. A. & Gidado, A. J. (2020). Assessment of the Perception of Security Men on Criminal Profiling as a Tool for Crime Control in Kaduna State, Nigeria. *The International Journal of Humanities & Social Studies*. 8(12).
- De Wet, J. A. (2013). *An exploratory analysis of serial rape in South Africa*. Retrieved from UP Space Institutional Repository.
- Department of Information and Communication Technology, Nigeria Police Force, (2020). *Functions of scene of crime/forensic science laboratory section*. <https://police.gov.ng/index.php/forensic>
- Douglas, E. J. & Burgess, A E. (1996) *Criminal Profiling: A viable investigative tool against Violent crime". 12 FBI Law Enforcement Bulletin*, 1-5.
- Ebisike, N. (2007). *The use of offender profiling evidence in criminal cases: Theses And Dissertations*. 23-43.
- Edero, A. E. (2020). *Criminal profiling: The forensics that links a crime scene behavior to a Suspect*. Retrieved <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2020/04/criminal-profiling-the-forensics-that-links-a-crime-scene-behavior-to-a-suspect/>
- Eigege, E. Y. (2006). *The role of the police in ensuring peace and security: The Nigerian experience*. An Unpublished B.sc Project, Department of Political Science, Benue State University.
- Elechi, O. O & Noel, (2018). *The Nigeria Police Forensic Investigation Failure*. *Journal of Forensic Sciences and Criminal Investigation*. Vol. 9 (1) May, 2018.

- El hajjar, S. T. (2018). Statistical analysis: Internal-consistency reliability and construct validity. *International Journal of Quantitative and Qualitative Research Methods*, 6(1), 27-38.
- Evelyn, U. (2021). Police PROs Schools on Forensic Sciences retrieved <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2021/09/police-pros-schooled-on-forensic-science/>
- Eysenck, H., & Eysenck, M. (1985). *Personality and individual differences*. New York: Plenum Press.
- Federal Bureau of Investigation, (2008). Investigative programs critical incident response Group. Retrieved 20 October, 2020. from <http://www.fbi.gov/hq/isd/cirg/ncavc.htm>
- Felson, M. (1987). Routine activities and crime prevention in the developing metropolis. *Journal of Criminology*, 25, 911-931.
- Holmes, R. M. (2000). *Murder in America* (2nd Ed), Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Hulin, C., Netemeyer, R. & Cudeck, R. (2001). Can a Reliability Coefficient Be Too High? *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, 10, 1,55-58.
- Ikenna, E. O. (2006). Policeman shoots colleague, Two Others, Over N20, Daily Trust, February 22nd.
- Ibrahim, I. F. R & Andrew E. Z. (2021). Assessing the Prevalence of Psychopathy among Criminal and Non-Criminal Population in Kaduna State Nigeria. *Kampala International University*. 6(3): 77-90.
- Iwerimie-Jaja, D. (2003). *Criminology: The study of crime*, Owerri, Springfield Publisher Ltd.
- Ismail, O. & Abiodun, A. (2008). Youth in the interface of development and security. *Journal of Conflict, Security and Development*. 7(1): 3– 26.
- Jackson, J., Van Hoppen, P. J. & Herbrink, J. (1993). Does the service meet the needs? Netherland Institute for the Study of Criminality mimeographed Report.
- Jacoby, J. (2004). *Classics of criminology* (3rd ed.). Long Grove, IL: Waveland Press.
- Juliet, O. A. & Oluwa, M. O. (2019). The State of Forensic Science in Crime Investigation and Administration of Justice in Nigeria. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research* 10(7), 2229-5518.
- Keltus, K. (2017). An assessment of the application and impact of forensic science in the Nigerian criminal justice system. A project submitted to the faculty of law Ahmedu Bello University, Zaria, in partial fulfilment for the award of LL.B Degree.
- Kocsis, R. N. (2013). *Applied criminal psychology: A guide to forensic behavioural sciences*, Charles C Thomas Publisher.

- Krippendorff, K. (1980). *Content analysis: An introduction to its methodology*. Beverly Hills CA: Sage Publications.
- Labuschagne, G. N. (2006). The use of linkage analysis as evidence in the conviction of the Newcastle serial murder, South Africa, *Journal of Investigative Psychology & Offender Profiling*, 3(3), 183-191.
- Levi-Minzi, M. & Shields, M. (2007). Serial sexual murders and prostitutes as their victims: difficulty profiling perpetrators and victim's vulnerability as illustrated by the Green River Case. *Brief Treatment and crisis Intervention*, 7(1) 77-89.
- Lombroso, C. (1876). *Criminal Man: Edition 1* In *Criminal Man*. (2006) Edited and translated by Mary Gibson and Nicole Hahn Rafter, 39– 96. Durham, NC: Duke Univ. Press.
- Metropolitan Police Service, Jack The Ripper, A <http://Content.Met.Police.Uk/Site/Jacktheripper>
- Michael, G. M. (2000). Criminal profiling: Is there a role for the forensic Psychiatrist? *Journal of American Academy of Psychiatry and Law*, 28(3), 319.
- Muller, D. A. (2000). Criminal profiling: Real science or just wishful thinking? *Homicides Studies*, 4, 234-241.
- Muhammad, Z. S. (2022). Forensic Intelligence, Databases, and the Challenges of Forensic Investigations in the Nigeria Police Force: An Empirical Study. *Southern Journal of Research* 2(1), 2022
- Neild, R. (2007). *Anti-corruption and police integrity*. USAID Program Brief: Security Sector Reform. P.12.
- Nte, U. N., Nte, N. D., Enokie, B. K. & Bienose, O. (2019). DNA profiling and the challenges of crime management in Nigeria Police. *Journal of Indonesian Legal Studies* 4(2), 2019.
- Nunnally, J. C. & Bernstein, I. H. (1994). *Psychometric Theory* (Ed.3). *New York: McGraw Hill*.
- Nwokolo, M. & Ivongbe I, (2022). A review of the forensic science evidence admissibility for handling criminal prosecution in Nigeria. *Law Audience Journal* 3(4) 284-3000.
- Nykodym, N., Taylor, R. & Vilela, J. (2005). Criminal profiling and insider cyber crime. *Computer Law & Security Review*, 21(5), 408– 414.
- Odekunle, F. (1979). The Nigeria police force: A preliminary assessment of functional Performance. *International Journal of Sociology of Law*.7: 61 – 83.
- Odekunle, F. (2005). “Crime and social deviance” in Akeredolu, A (ed) *Social Development in Nigeria*; Ibadan University Press Ltd, 68 – 71.

- Odekunle, F. (2004). Overview of policing in Nigeria: Problems and suggestions in crime and policing in Nigeria. Challenges and options.
- Onashile, Y. (2009). The Nigeria Police Force and forensic evidence, Quoted in Daily Champion 18th October.
- Oputa, A. I. (1975). Crime and the Nigerian society. *African Indigenous Laws*. University of Nigeria: Institute of African Studies.
- Otuba, A. K. & Coker, S. A. (2006). Police and crime prevention in Nigeria. *Journal of Modern African Studies*, 20(3), 411-430.
- Owens, D. (2006). Criminal minds the science and psychology of profiling: New York: Quintet Publishing Limited.
- Palermo, G. B. & Kocsis, R.N. (2005). Offender profiling: An introduction to the Socio-psychological analysis of violent crime. Springfield, Ill: Charles C. Thomas Publisher Ltd.
- Pinizzotto, A.J., Finkel, N. J. (1990). Criminal personality profiling: An outcome and Process study, *law and human behaviour*, 14, 215-233
- Woodhams, J. (2012). Offender profiling and crime linkage. In G. Davies, & A. Beech (eds), *Forensic psychology: Crime, justice, law, interventions* (2nd edition).
- Woodworth, D. & Porter, U. (2001). Historical foundations and current applications of criminal profiling in violent crime investigation. Kluwer Academic Publishers, Netherland.
- Richard, K. (2003). The science of offender profiling. *International Journal of Offender Therapy and Comparative Criminology*. 47,(2).
- Robert, R., Hazelwood. & Ann W. Burgess, (Eds), (2001). Practical aspects of rape Investigation: *A Multidisciplinary Approach*, 3rd edition.
- Robinson, J. P., Shaver, P. R. & Wrightsman, L.S. (1991). Criteria for scale selection and evaluation. *Meas Pers Social Psychology of Attitude*, 1(3), 1-6.
- Ronald, T. (2008). Criminal profile construction and investigative procedures. A study of the Westley Dodd Serial Sexual Murders. R. N. Kocsis © Humana Press, Totowa, NJ 2008.
- Rogers, M. (2003). The role of criminal profiling in the computer forensics process. *Computers & Security*, 22(4), 292– 298
- Schmallegger, F. (2008). Criminal justice: A brief introduction (7th ed.). Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Sethi, C. & Barney, K. F. (2017). Serial crime as occupation: Parallels between occupational analysis and psychological profiling. *Journal of Occupational Science*, 25(2), 283-289

- Siegal, L. (2008). *Criminology: The core* (3rd ed.). Belmont, CA: Cengage Learning.
- Siegal, L. (2009). *Criminology* (10th ed.). Belmont, CA: Cengage Learning.
- Stephen, O. O., Kelvin, O. O., Edeaghe, E. & Udogadi, N. S. (2021). Awareness level on the relevance of forensics in criminal investigation in Nigeria. *Journal of Forensic Science and Research*. 5; 053-057.
- Sylvester, O. & Agbeyi, M. (2019). The use of forensic evidence in criminal investigations. A study of Nigeria police force. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Research*. 5(2), 91-98.
- Tamuno, T. N. (1970). *The police in modern Nigeria. 1861-1965*. Ibadan University Press.
- Tamuno, T. N., Bashir, I.L., Alemika, E. O., Akano, A. O. (1993). *Policising Nigeria. Past, present, and future*. Panel on policising Nigeria project. Malthouse.
- The Nigerian police force website. www.npf.gov.ng
- The Nigerian police service commission website. www.sc.gov.ng
- Turvey, B. (1999). *Criminal Profiling: An introduction to behavioural science analysis*, M.S. San Diego, Academic Press.
- Turvey, B. (2002). *Criminal profiling: Introduction to Behavioral Evidence Analysis*, 1, San Diego Academic Press 2nd Edition 2002.
- Turvey, B. E. (2001). *Criminal profiling*. San Diego, CA: Elsevier Academic Press.
- Turvey, B. E. (2011). *Criminal profiling: An introduction to behavioural evidence analysis*. 3rd Edition. Academic Press.
- Udogadi, S. N. & Akpata, C. B. (2020). Awareness level on the role of forensic DNA database in criminal investigation in Nigeria: A case study of Benin city. *Journal of Forensic Science and Research*. 4; 007-014
- Ucheawaji, N. N., Nte, N. D. & Enokie, B. K., & Bienose, O. (2019). DNA profiling and the challenges of crime management in Nigeria. *Journal of Indonesian Legal Studies*. Published by Faculty of Law, University as Negeri Semarang, Indonesia. 4(2), 2548-1592.
- Wim, J., Katrien W., Patrick D. P. & Patrick V. K., (2008). *Marketing Research with SPSS*. Prentice Hall; Pearson Education. 978-0-273-70383-9. 274-275.
- Winerman, L. (2004). Criminal profiling: The reality behind the myth. *Monitor on Psychology*, 35(7), 66-69.